

D3.3

Level-2 Security Package for Resilience in Smart Factories: Final version

Project number:	871518
Project acronym:	COLLABS
Project title:	A COmprehensive cyber-intelligence framework for resilient coLLABorative manufacturing Systems
Start date of the project:	1 st January, 2020
Duration:	36 months
Programme:	ICT-08-2019

Deliverable type:	Report
Deliverable reference number:	DS-01-871518/ D3.3
Work package contributing to the deliverable:	WP3
Due date:	April 2022 - M28
Actual submission date:	29/04/2022

Responsible organisation:	Thales SIX GTS France (TSG)
Editor:	Thales SIX GTS France (TSG)
Dissemination level:	PUBLIC
Revision:	FINAL

Abstract:	This document provides a clear description of the COLLABS level-2 security components. In particular, it describes fine-grained authorization for constrained environments, relying on distributed ledger technologies for exchanges between different involved mechanisms. We show how COLLABS ledger-based security modules can secure inter-device communications and enhance the trust level in inter-
------------------	--

	device collaboration, on several aspects of the Smart Factory lifecycle. We describe how COLLABS ensures that all the data collected from connected objects, and all the actions are authorized following an effective security policy. This document also illustrates the main data flows with sequence diagrams, describing and visualizing processes involving each component, as well as mapping of COLLABS level-2 security components to the use case scenarios.
Keywords:	Fine Grained Authorization, Attribute based Access Control, Attribute based Encryption, Attribute based Decryption, Hyperledger Fabric, Public Key Infrastructure, Optiga TPM, Smart Contracts, Supply-chain, Confidential Data Discovery

The project COLLABS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 871518.

Editor

Thales SIX GTS France (TSG)

Contributors (ordered according to beneficiary numbers)

Foundation for Research and Technology Hellas (FORTH)

Infineon Technologies AG (IFAG)

Advanced Laboratory on Embedded Systems SRL (ALES)

University of Novi Sad Faculty of Sciences (UNSPMF)

Sphynx Technology Solutions AG (STS)

Renault SAS (REN)

Harokopio University (HUA)

Document Revisions & Quality Assurance

Internal Reviewers

1. SAG
2. UniPD

Revisions

Version	Date	By	Overview
0.1	15/11/2021	TSG	Initial ToC
0.2	04/03/2021	ALES, IFAG, TSG, UNSPMF	First round of inputs consolidation
0.3	08/04/2021	ALES, IFAG, TSG, UNSPMF	Second round of inputs consolidation
0.4	19/04/2021	TSG	Style fixing + preparation for post-review corrections
1.0	25/04/2021	ALES, IFAG, TSG, UNSPMF	Final version
1.1	27/04/2021	IFAG, TSG, UNSPMF	Ethics of AI addendum + minor fixes

Disclaimer

The information in this document is provided “as is”, and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The content of this document reflects only the author`s view - the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. The users use the information at their sole risk and liability.

Executive Summary

This deliverable provides an overview of the final version of the level-2 security components in COLLABS, related to the Resilience in the Smart Factories. The objectives of these components are to deliver tools for comprehensive access control, to design and deploy technologies based on blockchain and smart contracts applied for resilience in smart factories, to deliver the COLLABS public key infrastructure (PKI) mechanism, and to design and deliver tools and services for confidential data discovery. To fulfil these objectives, several components were developed in Work Package 3, some of them as individual enablers for new solutions and the others as complete systems with independent functionality.

In this document, readers will find three main features provided in the Level-2 Security Package: a blockchain-based fine-grained authorization system, a blockchain-based supply chain management system, and a confidential data discovery component. These features provide solutions in the area of comprehensive access control with a novel key infrastructure for Attribute-Based Encryption (ABE), in the supply-chain framework with a fast and smart system without trusted third parties, both based on blockchain and smart contracts, and for confidential data discovery. Moreover, the reader will find details about the technical components that enable these features, the Common Security Requirements (CSR) they cover, and the COLLABS use-cases in which they are relevant, these aspects being described in the document “D1.2: Positioning of COLLABS”.

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Translation
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
ABE	Attribute Based Encryption
IoT	Internet of Things
CA	Certification Authority
FGA	Fine Grained Authorization
ABAC	Attribute-Based Access Control
ECSO	European Cyber Security Organisation
PDP	Policy Decision Point
CP-ABE	Ciphertext-Policy Attribute Based Encryption
KP-ABE	Key-Policy Attribute Based Encryption
CSR	Common Security Requirement
IAM	Identity and Access Management
PEPs	Policy Enforcement Points
PKI	Public Key Infrastructure
TRNG	True Random Number Generator
HSM	Hardware Security Module
TTP	Trusted Third Party
MRO	Maintenance, Repair, and Overhaul
EVM	Ethereum Virtual Machine
TLS	Transport Layer Security
SoA	State-of-Art
CDD	Confidential Data Discovery
DPI	Deep Packet Inspection

Contents

- 1 Introduction11**
- 2 Level-2 Security Package for Resilience in Smart Factories12**
 - 2.1 Fine-Grained authorization based on ABE and Blockchain 12
 - 2.1.1 Architecture 13
 - 2.1.2 Protocol Execution 15
 - 2.1.3 Related work 16
 - 2.1.4 Summary of MVP version 17
 - 2.1.5 Summary of first complete version..... 17
 - 2.1.6 Summary of final version..... 17
 - 2.1.7 Integration in COLLABS Use Cases 18
 - 2.1.7.1 *ALES scenario #2 - Controlled Share of Compliance Data..... 18*
 - 2.1.7.2 *REN scenario #2 - Cloud-based architecture for industrial process 19*
 - 2.2 Blockchain-based supply chain management system 20
 - 2.2.1 Architecture 21
 - 2.2.2 Protocol Execution 22
 - 2.2.3 Related work 23
 - 2.2.4 Summary of MVP version 24
 - 2.2.5 Summary of first complete version..... 24
 - 2.2.6 Summary of final version..... 24
 - 2.2.7 Integration in COLLABS Use Cases 25
 - 2.2.7.1 *ALES scenario #3 - Trusted compliance data share across the supply chain..... 25*
 - 2.3 Confidential Data Discovery 26
 - 2.3.1 Architecture 26
 - 2.3.2 Protocol Execution 27
 - 2.3.3 Related work 27
- 3 Security Component Description29**
 - 3.1 Comprehensive Access Control..... 30
 - 3.1.1 Overview 30

- 3.1.2 Fine-grained authorization encryption module 31
 - 3.1.2.1 *Functional Description*..... 31
 - 3.1.2.2 *Integration*..... 31
- 3.1.3 Fine-grained authorization decryption module 31
 - 3.1.3.1 *Functional Description*..... 32
 - 3.1.3.2 *Integration*..... 32
- 3.1.4 Message Broker 32
 - 3.1.4.1 *Functional Description*..... 32
 - 3.1.4.2 *Integration*..... 33
- 3.1.5 Fine-grained authorization server 33
 - 3.1.5.1 *Functional Description*..... 33
 - 3.1.5.2 *Component Identity Form*..... 33
- 3.1.6 ABE key provider 34
 - 3.1.6.1 *Functional Description*..... 34
 - 3.1.6.2 *Component Identity Form*..... 34
- 3.1.7 Requirements (CSR fulfilment)..... 34
- 3.1.8 Future Work 36
- 3.2 Blockchains and Inter-Ledgers 36
 - 3.2.1 Overview 36
 - 3.2.2 Hyperledger fabric 37
 - 3.2.2.1 *Functional Description*..... 37
 - 3.2.2.2 *Component Identity Form*..... 38
 - 3.2.2.3 *Integration*..... 38
 - 3.2.3 IoT CA..... 38
 - 3.2.3.1 *Functional Description*..... 38
 - 3.2.3.2 *Integration*..... 39
 - 3.2.4 Hash Message Broker 39
 - 3.2.4.1 *Functional Description*..... 39
 - 3.2.4.2 *Component Identity Form*..... 39
 - 3.2.4.3 *Integration*..... 39
 - 3.2.5 Policies Server 39
 - 3.2.5.1 *Functional Description*..... 39
 - 3.2.5.2 *Component Identity Form*..... 39
 - 3.2.5.3 *Integration*..... 40
 - 3.2.6 Requirements (CSR fulfilment)..... 40

- 3.2.7 Future Work 42
- 3.3 Public Key Infrastructures 42
 - 3.3.1 Overview 42
 - 3.3.2 Optiga TPM 42
 - 3.3.2.1 *Functional Description*..... 42
 - 3.3.2.2 *Integration*..... 42
 - 3.3.3 Key provisioning for Remote attestation 43
 - 3.3.3.1 *Functional Description*..... 43
 - 3.3.3.2 *Component Identity Form*..... 43
 - 3.3.3.3 *Integration*..... 44
 - 3.3.4 Revocation binary tree 44
 - 3.3.4.1 *Functional Description*..... 44
 - 3.3.4.2 *Component Identity Form*..... 45
 - 3.3.4.3 *Integration*..... 47
 - 3.3.5 Requirements (CSR fulfilment)..... 47
 - 3.3.6 Future Work 48
- 3.4 Confidential Data Discovery 48
 - 3.4.1 Overview 48
 - 3.4.2 Components of CDD 48
 - 3.4.2.1 *Functional Description*..... 49
 - 3.4.2.2 *Component Identity Form*..... 50
 - 3.4.3 Integration..... 50
 - 3.4.4 Performance Evaluation..... 51
- 4 Ethics of Artificial Intelligence 52**
- 5 Summary and Conclusion..... 53**
- 6 Bibliography 54**

List of Figures

Figure 1: Architecture of the blockchain-based fine-grained authorization system..... 13

Figure 2: Protocol of the blockchain-based fine-grained authorization system 15

Figure 3: ALES scenario #2 - Controlled Share of Compliance Data 18

Figure 4: Final scheme of the system Fine-Grained authorization based on ABE and Blockchain..... 19

Figure 5. Renault Data Capture Infrastructure 20

Figure 6: Architecture of blockchain-based supply chain management system 21

Figure 7: Sequence diagram of SmartCard as HW tagging implementation showing the process of transferring the ownership to the distributor..... 22

Figure 8: Endpoint to business secure expansion of the blockchain-based SCM..... 25

Figure 9: CDD - Architecture of platform for network traffic monitoring and analysis 27

Figure 10: Fine-grained authorization using attribute-based encryption 31

Figure 11: Diagram of Hyperledger Fabric from..... 38

Figure 12: Example of the functionality of Revocation binary tree. 46

Figure 13: Data transformation within the CDD component. 49

Figure 14: NLP based ML model create a vectorized representation for each n-gram..... 50

List of Tables

Table 1: The Template used for Component Description..... 29

Table 2: Component description for Message Broker 32

Table 3: Component description for the FGA server 33

Table 4: Component description for ABE key provider 34

Table 5: Common Security Requirements (CSR) - Comprehensive Access Control 35

Table 6: Component Description for the Policies Server 39

Table 7: Common Security Requirements (CSR) - Blockchains and Interledgers 40

Table 8: Hyperledger Fabric Modules Software Requirements 41

Table 9: Component Identity Form for Remote attestation key provisioning..... 43

Table 10: Component Identity Form for Revocation binary tree 45

Table 11: Common Security Requirements (CSR) - Public Key Infrastructures 47

Table 12: Component Identity Form for Confidential Data Discovery 50

1 Introduction

The fourth industrial revolution, Industry 4.0, aims to enhance automation, productivity, quality, reliability, safety and efficiency in various industrial sectors including manufacturing [1]. Industrial 4.0 smart manufacturing improves efficiency, productivity, resilience, and sustainability through the smart factory and smart supply chain. For example, a smart factory enables a new level of automation in terms of machine self-diagnosis, self-repair, process optimization, and decentralized production control. Therefore, the smart manufacturing system can better detect errors and resist to unexpected events, achieving a sustainable success of the system despite attacks, failures, or misfortune. Smart supply chain enables highly integrated, transparent, and self-management supply chain by digital technologies and modern communication systems. Through digitization and connectivity, a higher level of productivity, reduced costs, increased profitability and reduced downtime can be achieved. The fundamentals of Industry 4.0 is to incorporate the modern digital technology to physical productions and operations with a focus on interconnectivity, machine learning, and real-time monitoring and control [2]. Rapid advancements in Information Technology (IT) and industrialization methods have expedited the advent of Industry 4.0 also known as integrated industry smart manufacturing or industrial internet. The notion of Industry 4.0 promises unprecedented progress in next generation of manufacturing technology by fundamentally changing the ways of production and value creation with the help of digital transformation in product/service offerings and horizontal/vertical value chains. Industry 4.0 is underpinned by a spectrum of emerging technologies such as cyber physical systems, internet of things, machine learning, adaptive robotics, artificial intelligence, cloud computing, Industrial Integration, and Service Oriented Computing. Distributed ledger technology also known as blockchain can not only affect Industry 4.0 but also has its direct implications in the above-mentioned set of technologies [3].

In this document, we present the Level-2 Security Package for Resilience in Smart Factories, which provides confidentiality, integrity, authenticity, authorization, non-repudiation and accountability to Industry 4.0 technologies. We present it through its main features, the blockchain-based fine-grained authorization system, the blockchain-based supply chain management system, and the Artificial Intelligence (AI) based confidential data discovery. We also detail the different technical subcomponents which implement these features, and their relevance in real-world use case scenarios, provided by the use-case providers Collins Aerospace, Renault, and Philips Consumer.

2 Level-2 Security Package for Resilience in Smart Factories

COLLABS defines multiple-levels of security mechanism, consisting of three security levels:

- The first level consists of hardware-enabled and device-level security mechanisms
- The second level includes security-enabling functionalities based on distributed ledger technologies.
- The third level of security corresponds to applying system-wide machine learning-based techniques to provide contextual awareness and deliver cognitive security-enabling mechanisms.

The scope of this document is to describe the level-2 security mechanisms. In particular, level-2 corresponds to information exchange between the devices within the boundaries of the smart factory. Therefore, in this deliverable we describe how in COLLABS:

- ledger-based security modules can secure inter-device communications and enhance the trust level in inter-device collaboration, on several aspects of the Smart Factory lifecycle;
- comprehensive and decentralized access control is used to protect the Smart Factory assets, relying on a fine-grained authorization module and ensuring that all the data collected from connected objects, and all the actions are authorized following an effective security policy;
- public key infrastructures (PKI) are used for identification and authentication purposes;
- data sensitivity can either be manually identified by design, or automatically using machine learning algorithms through confidential data discovery.

In the following subsections, we provide a clear picture about the main systems as well as an example of their interactions, and their integration in COLLABS use cases. One of the main efforts in WP3 for the final version is the integration of the projects in emulations of real environments (laboratories). The three use-case providers (PLC, ALES, REN) undertook the effort and collaborated in order to deploy the developed components of COLLABS in their corresponding laboratories, simulating their real manufacturing environments as if they could fit with the proposed scenarios.

Therefore, the components developed under WP3 were integrated in those laboratories in which some synergies with the scenarios could be found.

Divided by use-case owners (ALES, REN and PCL), the reader can find the mapping of the projects “Fine-Grained authorization based on ABE and Blockchain”, “Blockchain-based supply chain management system” and “Confidential Data Discovery” within each COLLABS scenario.

2.1 Fine-Grained authorization based on ABE and Blockchain

The Fine-Grained authorization system is designed to enable Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) to the smart factory. In this system, several actors can share data produced by multiple sensors, without having to deploy a frontal gateway to manage authorization.

A sensors’ owner can specify different rules for all kind of data produced by its sensors, with fine-grained definition. It relies on Attribute-Based Encryption (ABE), to provide end-to-end confidentiality and access control enforcement, manageable by policies, and lightweight enough to be directly embedded into sensors. This aspect is further described in [4].

In combination with a distributed architecture like Blockchain and OpenID, the fine-grained authorization system can dynamically distribute encryption policies and decryption key, and implement a master encryption keys rolling to enable revocation. Moreover, with blockchain we manage

dynamically the certificates and revoke the actors in runtime. Used along with hardware security components, this provides a secure infrastructure with strong authentication of the actors and strong integrity of the data/information exchanges.

2.1.1 Architecture

The proposed system architecture is depicted in Figure 1. It consists in providing fine-grained access control to the stakeholders of sensors data sharing, that communicate with the smart contracts to govern the access control of the encrypted data stored on an Interplanetary File System (IPFS) [5]. Such parties include the sensor owner, the client, the sensors devices, the message broker (IPFS) and smart contracts (blockchain).

Figure 1: Architecture of the blockchain-based fine-grained authorization system

Our decentralized fine grained authorization framework using blockchain technology system provides integrity and traceability. The distributed ledger of the blockchain-based solution acts as an immutable evidence for all the transactions recorded on it. It provides traceability features for access control related events. This system assures all participating entities that the data stored on it cannot be modified or tampered with, thereby enforcing trust. Our blockchain-based solution maintains a chain of hashes, wherein each block uses the hash of the previous block. Therefore, altering one bit in a block leads to invalidating all the blocks that follow it.

The revocation of the system is provided through indirect revocation. It means that when needed, all the decryption keys will be cancelled, and new decryption keys are provided just to non-revoked users. The decryption keys cancelation is done through an update of the encryption policies. All the encrypted messages include in the policy a particular version ($V \in \mathbb{N}$). Only decryption keys with attribute V can decrypt the message. When a user is revoked, all the encrypted messages include in the policy the new version $V+1$. Therefore, all users with attribute V need to update their decryption keys, but just non-revoked users will be able to. For this system to work, it requires a dynamic private key exchange structure, and a reliable and always available policy provider.

Our system includes the following elements in order to provide a fine-grained authorization system based on attribute-based encryption [4]:

- **Sensor owner:** It represents the owner and responsible of the architecture.
- **Client(s):** It refers to readers of the data stored in the system. Every client has a unique address used to interact with the blockchain.
- **Policy:** Group of attribute combinations necessary to decrypt a particular message.
- **Sensors:** Our assumptions are as follows:
 - Every sensor has an attached policy, which has to be satisfied to decrypt the sent messages of this sensor.
 - Various sensors can have the same policy.
 - Every sensor has an address to interact with the blockchain.
- **Smart contract:** Smart contracts are programs that are executed and hosted on the blockchain [6]. All the operations and stored data in these programs are semi-public. We consider the smart contract as always trusted, because the execution is always correct, and the stored data cannot be faked. Also, all the interactions with the smart contract are authenticated and recorded in the blockchain.
 - **Policies server:** This server stores the policies used in ABE. This policies are needed to encrypt de data using ABE. One of the important information stored here is the current version of the decryption key needed to decrypt the message. It is a smart contract and only the sensor owner can modify this smart contract getting the needed reliability and availability.
 - **IoT CA:** It is a smart contract that keeps an updated list of the authorized sensors.
 - **Hash message broker:** It stores the metadata of every message sent by the sensors. There are 4 variables to store for each message: (hash_, address_, t_,nonce_). hash_ is the hash of the message sent by the sensor; address_ is the address of the sensor that sent the message ; t_ is the time when the metadata was uploaded to the blockchain; and nonce_ is the number of the version of the ABE policy that was used to encrypt the data.
- **Message broker:** It is an Interplanetary File System (IPFS). It refers to a Peer-to-Peer (P2P) decentralized database that holds the data, and stores every encrypted message linked to its hash.
- **ABE key provider:** It is a web service, which manages ABE master keys and has 2 endpoints:

- /public: provides master public key for encryption purposes
- /private: requires OpenID Connect [7] authentication, provides an authenticated user the ABE decryption key generated from his attributes
- **Identity provider:** It is an Identity and Access Management (IAM) service that:
 - manages clients and their attributes
 - provides OpenID Connect [7] authentication

2.1.2 Protocol Execution

In the following, we illustrate an example of interactions among the system entities. The global protocol that leverages all level-2 security components follows the following steps as depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Protocol of the blockchain-based fine-grained authorization system

- **Step 0:** The sensor owner updates the policies server and gets the ABE master public key from the ABE key provider that is configured with a trusted ID provider.
- **Step 1:** The sensor reads its policy from the Policies server and encrypts its message. The policy is always using “and nonce”.
- **Step 2:** The sensor sends the hash of the message to the Hash Message Broker signed using a Hardware Security Module (go to D4.3 section “3.1.2 Optiga™ TPM as key store for blockchain” for more information) and sends the encrypted message and the hash to the Message Broker (IPFS). Then, the Hash Message Broker and the IPFS verify the identity of the sensor using the IoT CA in order to accept or to deny the storing.
- **Step 3:** The client connects with the Hash Message Broker and provides the address of the sensor to read. Then, the client reads the metadata, checks if he has the correct Attribute based encryption key version, and then downloads the hash of that message.
- **Step 4:** Using the hash, the client downloads the corresponding encrypted message from the IPFS.
- **Step 5:** The client asks the ABE key provider for its decryption key. The ABE key provider asks it first to authenticate and redirects it to the ID provider for authentication
- **Step 6:** Once authenticated, the ID provider gives the clients attributes to the ABE key provider.

- **Step 7:** The ABE key provider generates the decryption key using the client's attributes, and returns it to the client. The client tries to decrypt the message coming from the IPFS using the given decryption key. It will succeed to decrypt it if the attributes of the client are compatible with its policy. If it succeeds, the client checks the veracity of the message comparing it with the hash.

2.1.3 Related work

There are many theoretical works in the literature proposing the use of Attribute Based Encryption (ABE) with an efficient user management and revocation system, such as [8] [9] [10]. However, these works remain in the theoretical framework without proposing an effective implementation of the system.

One of the main objectives of this work will be to present the real implementation of a real Hybrid Revocable ABE scheme based on [8], and using the blockchain support to manage the dynamic refresh of the encryption policies, the data index, and the verified sensors node key infrastructure. Also, it uses OpenID for dynamic updates of private keys.

There are several approaches that propose to mix ABE and blockchain:

In [11], Rahulamathavan et al. created a new blockchain framework combining the SoA encryption techniques and the blockchain technology to preserve the privacy of transactions. ABE controls who can "see and use" the transaction data. This approach has two main disadvantages: the first one is that stores all the data in the ledger, i.e., in the block mined. It causes an overhead of any public blockchain PoW-based. For example, storing a 256-bit word in Ethereum has a price of 20000 gas [12] which at the current time is \$3.23476. The second problem is that every transaction can only be verified by the miners with the right attributes, therefore if we are trying to verify a transaction with very unusual attributes, just a few miners could verify it which would lead to a trust leak.

In [13], S. Wang et al. propose an implementation of blockchain-based ABE data sharing using an Interplanetary File System (IFS) to store the data. It is similar to our proposal, but the main difference is that they do not include a revocation system in their implementation.

The work [14] presents a novel fine-grained authorization system based in a interesting ABE algorithms with a dynamically key management. Just by changing the public parameters the users can be added and removed to/from the system. But this proposed scheme exposes three problems for our scenario:

- **Public parameters size:** The size of the public parameters is the production of the readers and the attributes, and since we want to use IoT devices to encrypt data, it is a problem to need such size of public parameters to encrypt the data.
- **Data re-encryption:** Every time one user is added to the system, the data should be re-encrypted which, in the long-term, leads to an overhead of the servers.
- **IoT device trust:** The proposed wearable devices (IoT devices) interact with the system, but they do not propose a reliable way to store the private keys to interact with the blockchain and to use these keys in the IoT device.

Our proposed offers a versatile management system for refresh decryption keys with indirect revocation, meanwhile mixing it with a novel direct revocation mechanism to provide a real-time revocation and hosting the main (single-point of failure) nodes of this system in blockchain to guarantee high availability, integrity, and no data repudiation.

2.1.4 Summary of MVP version

In the context of COLLABS MVP, we have developed the following list of modules:

- **Blockchain:** An example ledger used for development proposed of “Hyperledger Fabric” was implemented in the MVP version. Not valid for final applications.
- **Sensor:** Together with the blockchain, we developed the sensors with a hardware security module (“Optiga TPM”) to manage the private keys and the interaction with the blockchain and “Fine-grained authorization encryption module” to encrypt the generated data.
- **IoT CA:** A smart contract that store the identifications of the sensors nodes and can only be modified by authorized entity.
- **Hash message broker:** A smart contract that stores the digest of the messages uploaded by sensor nodes validated by the IoT CA.
- **Message broker:** A centralized version of the message broker was developed, able to receive information from external nodes, and use the “IoT CA” to verify the authority of the input data.
- **Client:** A client was developed. It can read data from the blockchain, use it to ask to the message broker for the desired data, and finally decrypt it using Fine-“Grained Authorization decryption module”.

In the MVP, just the main parts to enable the functionality of the system is developed. All the section related with the key distribution (ABE keys and public keys) is missing; therefore, for the correct functionality of the MVP version, the ABE keys, public keys and certificates have to be pre-stored in the devices.

2.1.5 Summary of first complete version

The efforts in this first complete version were focused in:

- **Blockchain:** It has been developed a dedicated structure to fit the project objectives. This new framework is valid for final applications.
- **Sensor:** The module “fine-grained authorization encryption module” was transferred from a Docker container to direct implementation in the sensor for a more efficient development since it is an IoT device.
- **Message broker:** We have created a Docker container version of the server, to facilitate the integration.
- **Integration:** The full system was integrated in ALES lab, and the functionality was validated.
- **Client:** We added the message digest verification to the client, which was omitted at MVP level
- **Authorization management:** an application to publish encryption policies, manage ABE master keys and generate client’s decryption keys.

2.1.6 Summary of final version

For the final version, the focus was placed on:

- **ABE key provider:** The module focused on the ABE keys management. It allows to create ABE master key pair and generate individual ABE decryption keys from an attributes set.

- **ID provider:** An identity provider compatible with OpenID Connect [7] is required here. The product used to fill this function is Keycloak [15].
- **Fine-grained authorization server:** A web service that encapsulates the ABE key provider with an OpenID Connect [7] interface for client authentication and an ABE decryption key generation using the attributes provided by the identity provider.
- **Decentralized Message broker:** The node was decentralized, allowing the component being deployed in different machines at different locations to improve the availability.
- **Policies server:** Smart contract that stores the current policy for every sensor. Because its characteristics -high reliability, availability and high updated status- can be used for a dynamic change of policies, ideal for indirect-revocation.

2.1.7 Integration in COLLABS Use Cases

The fine-grained authorization system based on ABE and blockchain has been identified as relevant for the following scenarios.

2.1.7.1 ALES scenario #2 - Controlled Share of Compliance Data

This scenario envisions the need of securely sharing the data produced in the shop floor during the manufacturing process within the company (at different levels), but also outside of the company in order to exploit third party services like cloud-based data analysis. A high-level representation of the data-flows envisioned for this scenario is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: ALES scenario #2 - Controlled Share of Compliance Data

In D3.2 [16], we highlighted the mapping of the component on the scenario and provided an overview of the deployment architecture.

The final version of “Fine-Grained authorization based on ABE and Blockchain” includes “Policy server” and “Fine-grained authorization server”. With the “Policy Server”, the data sources can keep the policies up-to-date; with renewed policies this nodes can encrypt messages providing data access only to data consumers with an updated decryption key, which is dynamically provided to the clients by the “Fine-grained authorization server”. These two components combined, provide key revocation capabilities to the system.

Figure 4: Final scheme of the system Fine-Grained authorization based on ABE and Blockchain

2.1.7.2 REN scenario #2 - Cloud-based architecture for industrial process

The infrastructure schema depicted in Figure 5 illustrates the communication in REN plants for OT/IloT services and industrial processes. In REN lab, standard industrial devices (industrial desks, IloT gateways, etc.) exchange continuously with production servers and operational devices using standard protocols (tcp/ip, profinet, modbus, S7...). At facility level, edge devices communicate with OT devices (robots, automatons, ...) and implement OPC-UA¹ server. At plant level, a data flow aggregator component collects data from OPC-UA servers and transfers JSON encapsulated data through MQTT², to a cloud data lake.

REN lab infrastructure for scenario #2 will be further described in COLLABS deliverable D6.2 [17].

¹ <https://opcfoundation.org/about/opc-technologies/opc-ua/>

² <https://mqtt.org/>

Figure 5. Renault Data Capture Infrastructure

In this context, Fine-grained authorization (FGA) is applicable for access control on captured data. It will enable the confidentiality of this data and allow collaboration between plants or with partners, through the cloud, while enforcing strict access control on this data.

In order to ensure confidentiality of data coming from the plant, an FGA encryption module can be embedded on local gateway level for edge device data protection, or deployed at data flow aggregator level for aggregated data protection. The plant can host blockchain nodes containing the FGA system smart contracts, and the message broker can either be in the cloud or local to the plant, regarding the wished scope of the data (i.e., whether the data consumer is local to the plant or outside).

2.2 Blockchain-based supply chain management system

A Supply Chain Management system (SCM) is a functionality used to control the stream of goods, finances and data related to a product, from the acquisition of raw materials to the delivery of the final product at its final customer. Sometimes this system can also include control over Maintenance, Repair, and Overhaul (MRO) operations.

It is common belief that supply chain corresponds to logistic management; however this is just one feature of the entire system. With the increase in digitalization and automation that characterize the current industrial manufacturing environment the supply chain includes not only material tracking but also software interaction, data handling and order fulfilments. The system must integrate interaction from all the parties involved in a product lifecycle such as manufacturers, logistic companies, suppliers and possibly control authorities.

In this scenario, we can see a supply management system as a distributed system that requires collaboration between untrusted parties that work towards a common target. This structure along its requirements has been implemented on a blockchain, which is an established design for collaborative use cases in a distributed (and untrusted) environment. The functionalities of the system are detailed in the following sections.

2.2.1 Architecture

The proposed design, depicted in Figure 6, implements a management system for an example supply chain.

Figure 6: Architecture of blockchain-based supply chain management system

The main components of the system are:

- **Hyperledger Fabric blockchain:** distributed ledger that stores all the information contained in the system under the form of transactions.
- **PKI system:** each component of the blockchain is authenticated and authorized through a certification authority controlled by one of the participant organizations
- **Smart contract:** code that regulates all the interaction with the system. It encodes a business process that must be respected in the supply chain. It does also enforce fine-grained rules for data access
- **Private collections:** in the HLF blockchain data can be stored in these structures to specify precise access rules between a subset of organizations that participate in the HLF network. Each private collection has its own fine-grained permissions configuration.
- **Trusted platform module:** hardware security device used as the root of trust of the IoT key management.

- **Hardware tagging system:** crypto-enabled chips are integrated in the system to provide strong tracking capabilities for the supplies. This enhances the link between the physical world and its cyber representation

2.2.2 Protocol Execution

The system has been designed and implemented with security as primary goal. In particular, the component focuses on the following security properties:

1. Authentication and authorization of all the system participants
2. Strict data access control with different rules for different participants
3. Data encryption to protect the communication between the network components
4. Non-repudiation and immutability of the data stored on the system
5. Strong link between physical and cyber world

The first four items have been thoroughly explained in D2.2 Sec. 2.2.2. In this section we focus on detailing the (5) bullet, connection between the physical world and its cyber representation.

To enhance the link between the physical good tracked by the SCM and its data stored on the distributed ledger we exploited a Hardware Security Module (HSM) with cryptographic capabilities that is usually used in smart cards but that could be physical attached to any item and used through NFC; particularly we use the product SLJ52GDA111CS³, part of the SECORA™ ID security solutions from Infineon Technologies. This chip offers capabilities such as key generation, secure key storage, hashing, and digital signing.

Figure 7: Sequence diagram of SmartCard as HW tagging implementation showing the process of transferring the ownership to the distributor.

³ <https://www.infineon.com/cms/en/product/security-smart-card-solutions/secora-security-solutions/secora-id-security-solutions/slj52gda110cs>

In our approach we used the signing capabilities of this chip to validate each ownership transfer throughout the entire supply chain lifecycle. The chip generates a X.509 certificate and stores securely its own private key. This private key is then used to sign each ownership transfer which is registered on the distributed ledger. The smart contract managing the SCM interaction accepts only ownership transfers which are signed with the chip private key (easily checked with the public key) and approved by the new owner. Therefore, only someone who has access to the chip (which is physically attached to the good that is being tracked) can perform this valid signature and with it getting the ownership over the supply. In Figure 7 we show an example of physical ownership transfer, in particular how the “distributor” interacts with the smart card to log on the distributed ledger its ownership of the tagged supply. As can be seen, there is no need for interaction with the last owner, just physical access to the package and approbation of the distributed ledger. For more details, please refer to D4.3, section 3.1.3 Secora ID card for packages identification in supply chain management system.

This technique enhances the integration of the blockchain, pushing computation and security capabilities toward the edge. This add strong tracking capabilities with cryptographic assurances in the broad end-to-end security approach that the blockchain-based supply chain management system is proposing. As shown in Figure 8, this research focuses on adding to the common horizontal supply chain representation (business to business) a secure vertical integration to include in the process the edge industrial devices deployed in the organization shop floor.

2.2.3 Related work

The collaborative manufacturing environment prompted by the Industry 4.0 revolution leads to an overall increment of data collected throughout the entire product lifecycle. SCM, to properly coordinate different players involved in the production process, require a transparent understanding of the available data flows and partner relationships [18]. The increase in (automatic) data flows between supply chain partners impose a redesign from a security point of view of the supply chain concept. In this context, blockchain technologies are proposed in the literature for their intrinsic transparency, traceability and non-repudiation properties that can be exploited in the supply chain management systems [19].

In various industrial compartments, blockchain technologies for supply chain management have been explored. For example, usage of blockchain for SCM in the additive manufacturing supply chain has been explored in [20] where an analysis of the advantages and adoption for blockchain is presented. An architecture to integrate IIoT from the textile manufacturing world in a blockchain-based system is proposed in [21]. Also, in the avionics industry we have some exploration going on with [22] that analyzed from a high level prospective pros, cons and gaps of blockchain technologies applied to aircraft parts managements business process.

In our approach, we explore blockchain application for SCMs with a specific focus on secure edge integration, focusing on pushing computation and security features toward the shop-floor to provide an end to end security framework. This work analyze the results from a security point of view inspecting and validating the security guarantees provided by specific blockchain framework used (Hyperledger Fabric) investigating enforcement of data confidentiality and the enforcement of the least knowledge principle. Moreover, the approach integrates hardware security modules that act as root of trust to enhance integrity, origin and non-repudiation guarantees on the data produced while manufacturing on the industrial machines. On top of that the physical goods managed through the SCM are tagged using HW tracking chips that are used to enhance the link between the physical world and its cyber representation. In particular, these chips are used to provide cryptographic guarantees about the part ownership throughout the entire supply chain lifecycle. At the best of our knowledge there is no other

work that focuses on integrating security in the vertical supply chain to enhance the overall SCM process.

2.2.4 Summary of MVP version

For the MVP, we implemented a single channel, including four organizations. This first prototype demonstrates the technology with a simple smart contract that manage the interaction in a portion of the supply chain. All the components required to handle the blockchain were deployed in the laboratory and a first test has been performed.

2.2.5 Summary of first complete version

The first complete version of the technology includes a more complex smart contract handling more interactions between the MVP organizations. Moreover, a TPM have been integrated in the prototype to enhance security of a client placed on an IoT device. In this iteration, we also changed the configuration to obtain a fully encrypted communication between all the devices included in the distributed system.

2.2.6 Summary of final version

The complete version of the component proposes a supply chain management system based on a blockchain methodology with information segregation and high integrity guarantees. The solution focuses on properly regulate data access between different organizations while implementing secure vertical integration of the industrial devices in the SCM process. The prototype is implemented using Hyperledger Fabric, a framework for distributed ledger technology application that delivers high degrees of confidentiality, resiliency, flexibility and scalability. The approach enforces least privilege knowledge principle at design level by structuring the information with different access control rules matching the requirement defined by the specific use case using segmentation techniques to keep data confidentiality between trusted parties in the supply chain limiting the ability and knowledge of each party to what is required to perform its precise duty.

Figure 8: Endpoint to business secure expansion of the blockchain-based SCM

In order to push more security on the vertical integration (edge to business) the approach integrates HSM devices deployed directly on the data sources of the shop floor to provide root of trust guarantees on the compliance measurements produced and directly stored on the SCM by IIoT devices. Finally strong physical tracking capabilities are guaranteed by exploiting hardware tagging techniques which provide modern encryption functionalities. This approach is integrated in the system and is used to provide cryptographic guarantees about the ownership of each specific item tracked by the SCM, providing therefore strong non-repudiation and traceability assurances.

2.2.7 Integration in COLLABS Use Cases

The Blockchain-based supply chain management system has been identified as relevant for the following scenario.

2.2.7.1 ALES scenario #3 - Trusted compliance data share across the supply chain

The manufacturing of a complex and safety-critical system such as a jet engine requires manufacturing, transfer, integration and testing of a myriad mechanical and electronic parts. The manufacturing ecosystem collaborates in the supply chain to realize this coordination. Safety guarantees are provided by adherence of all parties to the highest standards of production and require appropriate justification of due diligence from all parties. Compliance data and its traceability are essential and the interaction between supply chain parties is greatly facilitated by digital means. Automation of these complex information flows requires to establish trust, guarantee integrity, support traceability and accountability, potentially without relying on a single central authority.

In D3.2 sec 4.1.2 is highlighted how the technology is deployed on ALES scenario 3, implementing different information access rules enforced using smart contracts assertions and private collection from Hyperledger Fabric.

Since this system collects information about products throughout the entire product manufacturing, is very important to have strong guarantees about physical location and ownership of each part during

this process. To track the parts a crypto chip is integrated in the system, in particular, they are aggregated to the supplies: this hardware provides functionalities to generate, store and securely interact with PKI information. With this system is possible to sign supply chain transactions with keys that only someone who have physical access to the specific hardware can operate, proving supply ownership. This is used to provide a strong link from the physical world to its cyber representation and hence, traceability non-repudiation, and supplies authentication.

In our prototype the hardware tagging chip is deployed on smartcards. In Figure 7 we can see how the system interacts with the smart card to sign and verify signatures. Basically, when an organization receives a product with the hardware tag, the first thing to do is to query the chip for its public key (i.e., certificate) and use it to corroborate that the product is exactly the one expected by verifying the signed hash stored on the SCM. After, the chip is used to sign a new hash value that will be stored on the ledger to prove the ownership change.

2.3 Confidential Data Discovery

Confidential data discovery (CDD) component is a network traffic analysis tool based on machine learning approach. Its basic characteristics are:

1. Flexible features selection process
2. Specific machine learning approach inspired by techniques from natural language processing domain

In a whole, the CDD component offers an adaptive approach, aimed at overcoming multiple challenges, including the fast analytics, accuracy and processing of packet data within different network protocols. The main goal is to create an effective way to monitor and analyse different network traffic types in a smart factory environment.

At the application level, CDD can be used in two ways:

- **Packet header data inspection** - with a goal of unusual and suspicious traffic detection, network attacks detection etc.
- **Packet payloads analysis** in the case of unencrypted traffic. This feature could be used for detection of private or confidential data leakage, among others.

2.3.1 Architecture

The UNSPMF Confidential Data Discovery (CDD) component implements predictive models using NLP based machine learning techniques, such as bag-of-words and sentence embedding. In order to make it possible, component performs a specific transformation of the incoming packet data stream into a set of tuples that mimics words in natural language. Depending on the data used for tuples creation, component is able to identify the unusual activities or a new network traffic pattern but also sensitive or confidential information exchange. Figure 9 shows the main components of the proposed system. For the first stage of the analysis, this component performs a basic network packet filtering, rejecting the uninteresting traffic. The tuple generation component generates an output that is fed to the ML component for further analysis in the second stage. The third and final stage is related to final alarms logic and sending the results to the component handling visualization.

Figure 9: CDD - Architecture of platform for network traffic monitoring and analysis

The benefits of such architecture are two-fold:

- On the feature level, it enables usage of protocol/domain specific features. This will improve our ML models for behaviour-based anomaly detection by overcoming the fuzzy representations with protocol independent features.
- On the application level, it enables utilization of light-weighted ML models that do not require high processing power and expensive hardware, designed for specific network's topics (protocols). Consequently, this could enable distributed processing.

2.3.2 Protocol Execution

As a first stage of the analysis, CDD component captures network data from a network interface or pcap files. Packet filtering rejects the uninteresting traffic so in the second stage the component generates tuples belonging to a particular protocol. We refer to these tuples of attributes as words. CDD enables adaptive feature selection process so words could include different information from packet header data or from payload data. In the next stage, sequence of words will be transformed to embedded space and represented as a vector. In this way, incoming packet data stream is represented in a form suitable for ML inference (classification) in the final stage.

2.3.3 Related work

Network traffic monitoring and analysis techniques have received much attention in recent years. Having in mind today's speed and variations in network types, this task has created a number of challenges.

In general, there are two main approaches in network monitoring: shallow packet inspection (SPI) and deep packet inspection (DPI). The first one, SPI refers to the inspection of packet headers while the second one, DPI refers to processing data (packet payload) that being sent over a network. Also, regarding the detection methodology, network traffic monitoring and security analysis are based on two distinguish methods: signature-based and behaviour-based. Signature-based approach is based on

monitoring of inbound network traffic in order to find sequences or patterns that match a particular attack signature. The main characteristics of this approach are:

1. Easy to implement
2. Requires signature for each suspicious traffic pattern or network attack (and expert to identify them)
3. Requires accurate model definitions. A loose interpretation will generate false negatives while too strict interpretation will increase percentage of false positives identifications.

Regular expressions, as a method for signature-based packet inspection, have been used for a long time. It enables flexible representation of complex string patterns so it is widely used for network traffic classification by payload-based signature matching algorithms [23], for representing threat signatures for intrusion detection systems [24] or to perform DPI in network data flow streams [25].

On the other hand, behaviour-based approach creates a shape of normal network activity and compares the new traffic with created model in order to detect unusual patterns in network activity. This type of network monitoring systems uses AI and machine learning for analysing data on a network. In [26], Tuor at al. introduced tiered recurrent architecture (Recurrent neural network - RNN) which demonstrated superior performance on the Los Alamos National Laboratory Cyber Security dataset. In this work, authors showed that language modeling approaches are appropriate for addressing computer security log analysis. Similarly, Radford at al. [27] tried to overcome poor generalization of the rule-based approaches creating RNN model of network traffic and then evaluate the ability of this model to detect malicious activity on that network. In this work, specific language model is used to identify sequences of network activity that are outliers with respect to the model. In [28], authors introduced Net2Vec, a modular framework for data scientists to develop and deploy machine learning methods in data communication networks. In this framework, network packets are first transformed into sequences of tuples and deep learning models are then applied to the tuple sequences for network analytics.

3 Security Component Description

In this chapter, we state the security components for the level-2 in COLLABS. For each component, we will follow a description form. Additionally, we provide security requirements perceived by these components. However, if the component did not change from the MVP or 1st final version, the reader will find a reference to the COLLABS deliverables D3.1 [29] or D3.2 [16] and the description form of the component in the matter will be omitted.

In particular, for each COLLABS component, we provide its description, including the following information fields with their list of interaction components:

- **Component Name:** name of the level-2 COLLABS component;
- **Functionality:** description of the main component features;
- **Pre-conditions:** refers to the conditions that must be satisfied before interacting with the component.
- **Post-conditions:** refers to the conditions that will be satisfied after the component will be providing its functionalities;
- **Interaction Component List:** List of the interaction components. In particular, we provide the following fields:
 - **IComponent Name:** name of the component with whom the component is interacting
 - **Input and Output:** a short description of input and output data exchanged.

Table 1 below, provides the template to be used for describing the various COLLABS components.

Table 1: The Template used for Component Description

Component Name	<< Name of the component >>	
Functionality		
<< Brief description of your component functionalities >>		
Pre-condition		
<< Conditions that must be satisfied before interacting with the component >>		
Post-condition		
<< Conditions that must always be true after interacting with the component >>		
Interaction Component List		
<<List here the components with which your component interacts >>		
IComponent Name	Input and Output	
<< Name of the interacting component >>	(INPUT) or (OUTPUT)	

We also describe the Common Security Requirements (CSR) that are covered by the security components. Special attention will be paid to the cross-cutting CSR-13, 15, 16 and 23, highlighted in the tables below.

3.1 Comprehensive Access Control

3.1.1 Overview

The goal of comprehensive access control is to provide fine-grained authorization for constrained environments, relying on distributed ledger technologies for exchanges between different involved mechanisms.

Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC)⁴ is an access control paradigm in which permissions are a combination of subject, resource, action and environment attributes, enabling the definition of very fine-grained access control policies. A traditional ABAC architecture usually requires Policy Enforcement Points (PEPs) closer to the resources to protect. These PEPs rely on a Policy Decision Point (PDP) that has knowledge of the access control policy, with which they maintain a constant connection to respond their authorization decision requests. This PEP/PDP architecture enables great flexibility but is not suitable for constrained environments, due to its requirements in deployment resources and connectivity. Comprehensive access control aims to open constrained environments to ABAC, relying on techniques using Attribute-Based Encryption.

Attribute-Based Encryption (ABE)⁵ is an asymmetric cryptosystem in which the encryption and decryption keys are based upon attributes. In such a system, the decryption of a ciphertext is possible if and only if the attributes of the decryption key match the attributes of the ciphertext.

There are two different types of ABE schemes:

- **Ciphertext-Policy ABE (CP-ABE):** The ciphertext is encrypted using an encryption policy, which consists of a logical condition over attributes. The decryption key is derived from an attribute set. The decryption of a ciphertext is feasible if-and-only-if the attribute set used to derive the decryption key satisfies the encryption policy.
- **Key-Policy ABE (KP-ABE):** The ciphertext is encrypted using an attribute set. The decryption key is derived from a decryption policy, which consists of a logical condition over attributes. The decryption of a ciphertext is feasible if-and-only-if the attribute set used for the encryption satisfies the decryption policy.

⁴ Guide to Attribute Based Access Control (ABAC) Definition and Considerations
<https://www.nist.gov/publications/guide-attribute-based-access-control-abac-definition-and-considerations-1>

⁵ Attribute-Based Encryption for Fine-Grained Access Control of Encrypted Data
<https://eprint.iacr.org/2006/309.pdf>

Figure 10: Fine-grained authorization using attribute-based encryption

ABE enables to embed ABAC mechanisms in the encryption method. Using this technique, Figure 10 shows how sensors can protect the data they produce by encrypting it in ABE using given attributes, and only need to encrypt it once, no matter how many consumers are going to read this data - which is saving resources. A client that wants to consume such data will have to request an authorization service for an ABE decryption key. This authorization service has knowledge of the access control policy and the client attributes and can then derive an individual decryption key for the client, whose capacities are the strict reflection of the client permissions defined by the access control policy. The client can then get all data from all the sensors, but its decryption key will only be able to decrypt the data it is authorized to read.

3.1.2 Fine-grained authorization encryption module

3.1.2.1 Functional Description

The fine-grained authorization (FGA) encryption module allows an IoT device to protect the data it produces in a low-consumption way. It performs an ABE encryption over the produced data, using an ABE master public key and an encryption policy. Encryption policies are provided through the blockchain. For the Component Identity Form refer to [29].

3.1.2.2 Integration

To ease the deployment in IoT devices, the module has been transferred from a Docker container to direct implementation in the small board holding the sensor.

3.1.3 Fine-grained authorization decryption module

3.1.3.1 Functional Description

The fine-grained authorization (FGA) decryption module allows a client to read data protected using FGA system. It interconnects with FGA server to get a decryption key and decrypts as many data as it can. It collects data from a message broker, according to notifications from the blockchain. For the Component Identity Form refer to [29].

3.1.3.2 Integration

The module is provided as a Docker container in order to ease the deployment in the laboratories' infrastructure.

3.1.4 Message Broker

3.1.4.1 Functional Description

The Message Broker role is to ensure availability of published data to the requesters. It can be a component managed by a 3rd party or shared between organizations, as no particular trust is required regarding confidentiality of the data. Once the encrypted data is shared with one of the Message broker nodes, the node spread the data with the rest of the nodes to ensure the availability of this data.

Table 2: Component description for Message Broker

Component Name	Message Broker
Functionality	
This component gathers data from publishers and provides it to requesters. Requesters can obtain data from data hash.	
Pre-condition	
The storage space must be sufficient to store the data. It should be decentralized enough to ensure availability. All data is hashed and encrypted, therefore, no security properties are needed as precondition.	
Post-condition	
Because the decentralization, this component is always available for the client and sensors.	
Interaction Component List	
IComponent Name	Input and Output
FGA encryption module	From FGA encryption module: ABE-encrypted data
FGA decryption module	To FGA decryption module: ABE-encrypted data
Client Application	Message Broker → Client Application: Sends the stored encrypted data

CA IoT	CA IoT → Message Broker: Verify the address of the IoT devices that upload the data to the server
--------	---

3.1.4.2 Integration

Any of the multiples nodes of Message broker is deployed in Docker containers. At the beginning of one node deployment, it needs one or more addresses of other nodes. It will ask to the nodes for the complete IP list of the decentralized infrastructure.

3.1.5 Fine-grained authorization server

3.1.5.1 Functional Description

The fine-grained authorization server provides the ABE master public key, and integrates with an external authentication service do deliver a decryption key to an authenticated user. It uses OpenID Connect⁶ standard to accept an external Identity Provider (e.g. Keycloak IdP⁷) as a trusted source for user attributes. It also integrates with ABE key provider to manage ABE master keys and generate decryption keys according to attributes set.

3.1.5.2 Component Identity Form

Table 3: Component description for the FGA server

Component Name	Fine-grained authorization server
Functionality	
Fine-grained authorization server is a web service (REST) that provides ABE master public key and authenticates users to generate and deliver specific ABE decryption keys according to their attributes.	
Pre-condition	
Users are registered in an existing identity provider supporting OpenID Connect, which is trusted as attributes source.	
An ABE master key set is loaded in the ABE key provider.	
Post-condition	
A request to the public key returns the master public key set in the ABE key provider.	
A request to the private key requires authentication, and if successful, returns the ABE decryption key generated with the authenticated user's attributes.	
Interaction Component List	

⁶ [OpenID Connect | OpenID](https://openid.net/connect/) : <https://openid.net/connect/>

⁷ [Keycloak](https://www.keycloak.org/) : <https://www.keycloak.org/>

IComponent Name	Input and Output
ABE Key provider	To ABE Key Provider: attributes set From ABE Key Provider: ABE decryption key
IdP Keycloak	From IdP Keycloak: user attributes

3.1.6 ABE key provider

3.1.6.1 Functional Description

The ABE key provider manages ABE master keys (public & private) and generates user decryption keys from the master private key and an attributes set.

3.1.6.2 Component Identity Form

Table 4: Component description for ABE key provider

Component Name	ABE key provider
Functionality	
ABE key provider is a module can create an ABE master key pair, and generate ABE decryption keys from the ABE master secret key and an attributes set.	
Pre-condition	
The deployment target must satisfy the system requirements of OpenABE (https://github.com/zeutro/openabe).	
Post-condition	
ABE key provider generates master keys and decryption keys, such as, given a data encrypted with a given attributes policy and a given master public key, all (and only) decryption keys generated from the matching master secret key and an attributes list satisfying the policy can decrypt the data.	
Interaction Component List	
IComponent Name	Input and Output
FGA server	From FGA server: attributes set To FGA server: ABE decryption key

3.1.7 Requirements (CSR fulfilment)

Comprehensive Access Control covers Cross-Cutting CSR-13 and 15 (see Table 5).

Table 5: Common Security Requirements (CSR) - Comprehensive Access Control

CSRs	Coverage	Technology Mapping
CSR-01: Identification and Authentication	Fully	Publication of encrypted data in the system must be signed to ensure source authentication. Access to the data is enforced by the decryption capability, on which only entities with a decryption key that satisfies the encryption policy can decrypt data.
CSR-02: State-of-the-art cryptography	Fully	ABE is a state-of-the-art cryptosystem for data protection and authorization enforcement.
CSR-05: Identity and access management	Fully	The module enforces access control policy as an encryption policy. It relies on attributes defined by IAM system.
CSR-06: Fine-grained access control support	Fully	The module provides attribute-based access control mechanism.
CSR-11: Data integrity protection	Fully	All the data is stored together with a digest of the data-package making it unmodifiable.
CSR-13: Protection against denial-of-service	Fully	The decentralized aspect of Message Broker protects the system against denial-of-service
CSR-14: Data availability	Fully	The decentralized aspect of Message Broker protects data against loss or unavailability thanks to replication.
CSR-15: Online patching and update capabilities	Partial	Encryption policies are dynamically provided through the Policy Provider in the blockchain, and data persistence is strengthened thanks to replication such as it allows online patching and update capabilities. Most of the components are packaged as Docker containers, allowing easy update.
CSR-17: Fail-safe security mechanisms	Partial	Security mechanisms (such as signature verification) rely on blockchain for inputs, which limits by design the risks of unavailability. Moreover, the required inputs have a very low change frequency, so their hypothetical unavailability should not affect the service availability. However, it might be theoretically possible that a signature is refused due to a conjunction of a recently renewed authentication key and an unavailability of blockchain PKI.
CSR-18: Confidentiality wrt. cloud	Fully	The module provides an end-to-end encryption mechanism that ensures data confidentiality in transit and at rest on intermediate stopovers without right-to-know (such as cloud storage / message broker). Besides, ABE decryption key is protected in transit and at rest using public key encryption.
CSR-19: Mutual compliance with	Partial	The encryption module provides encryption conformant with encryption policies provided by the Policy Server.

other system / components		The FGA server provides ABE decryption keys in conformance with IAM attributes.
CSR-21: Multi-tenancy	Partial	The FGA server manages a master keyset and dynamically generates and provides the decryption keys. It is possible to use several instances of the FGA server to manage multiple keysets.

3.1.8 Future Work

A special attention should be paid to the underlying ABE cryptosystem used. There are several existing ABE algorithms and implementations that would need to be compared, and selected according to their specificities and vulnerabilities. This subject should be further studied.

The fine-grained authorization server usage with dynamic management of ABE master keys and ABE decryption keys generation enables multi-tenancy, but it could itself be multi-tenant by managing several keysets and federating several identity providers as attribute sources.

3.2 Blockchains and Inter-Ledgers

3.2.1 Overview

Blockchain or distributed ledger is a decentralized, publicly or privately verifiable and peer-to-peer system, which stores data and executes arbitrary logic known as smart contract. It maintains data integrity and consistency of smart contracts execution among nodes through various consensus protocols [30], [31]. It results in a server where the trust of the services provided remains in all the integrating nodes. If we have a big quantity of nodes or we trust in the few integrating nodes, the services provided by the blockchain can be considered as a root of trust.

There are 3 types of blockchain [32]:

- **Public blockchain:** Everyone can be a node and be part of the blockchain. Since untrusted nodes exist, the presence of several nodes is necessary to consider public blockchain as trusted. The interactions with the blockchain are expensive (16.57 euros store a KB in Ethereum at the moment this document was written [33]) and slow (15 seconds - 5 minutes for any interaction in Ethereum).
- **Private Blockchain:** Various nodes host the blockchain, but all these nodes belong to the same organization, the admin. It is a more controlled blockchain, since in order to interact with it you need permission from the admin, so it is as trust as the hosted entity. All the interactions with the blockchain are much faster (~Seconds/transactions) and cheaper (~cent/GB).
- **Consortium Blockchain:** It is a mix of private blockchain and public blockchain. In order to interact with the blockchain, the user needs a consent from an admin, but there are multiple admins belonging to different organizations. To incorporate a new node, an agreement between the different admins has to exist. There are fewer nodes than in a public blockchain, but the nodes are more trusted, so the blockchain is still trusted, does not have to depend on a trusted third party (TTP) like in a private blockchain, and it is cheap and fast.

In the use cases defined in deliverable “D1.1: Positioning of COLLABS”, privacy is a fundamental element for the system, so that, the blockchain should be private or consortium. Hyperledger is an

effort that develops blockchain networks for different scenarios, and it affords the use of general-purpose programming languages such as Java, Go and Node.js for smart contract design.

Hyperledger has multiple frameworks such as Hyperledger Borrow, Hyperledger Fabric, Hyperledger Grid, and Hyperledger Sawtooth. All of them are used to build enterprise blockchain for a consortium of organizations and have some differences between them. Hyperledger Fabric is a blockchain framework for developing applications or solutions with a modular architecture. It has privacy, flexibility, and decentralization, which make it perfect for COLLABS.

Hyperledger Fabric also bring us the possibility of using decentralized applications (DApps) prepared to be used with Ethereum Virtual Machines (EVM [34]). Therefore, we can develop exportable components to be used with different ledger compatible with EVM.

In the following section, the reader can find a detailed description about those blockchain components which were developed to be deployed in the projects of “Fine-Grained authorization based on ABE and Blockchain” and “Blockchain-based supply chain management system”.

3.2.2 Hyperledger fabric

3.2.2.1 Functional Description

Hyperledger Fabric is a framework developed by Hyperledger [35]. One of the key advantages of Hyperledger Fabric is that it allows entities to conduct confidential transactions without passing information through a central authority. This is accomplished through different channels that run within the network.

Its modular architecture achieves a great flexibility allowing components such as consensus and membership services to be plug-and-play together with a division of labor creating different roll nodes within the network.

The components that build an Hyperledger Fabric network are:

- **Ledger:** It is a tamper-resistant record of all the transactions of the blockchain. Every transaction that is approved by participant agreement (consortium) is added to the ledger. It is denoted by “L” in Figure 11.
- **Channel:** A network that connects all the blockchain components that are part of the specific network. Every channel has his own ledger. The different components of the blockchain can interact with the ledger of a channel if and only if are part of the channel. “C” in Figure 11 refers to Channel.
- **Peer node:** A node that is maintained by one of the organizations of the blockchain. It hosts the copy of the channel ledgers that the organization has access. Peer node is denoted by “P” in Figure 11.
- **Smart contract:** The smart contract provides a well-defined set of ways by which the ledger of a channel can be asked or updated by a client application. In Figure 11, a smart contract is denoted by “S”.
- **Certification authority:** Every organization has his own certification authority that authorizes the rest of the components to interact with the blockchain, this refers to “CA” in Figure 11.
- **Client application:** It is the minimal requirement to interact with the blockchain. It just has a private key and a certificate of its organization. It can interact with the ledger by using the smart contracts of the channels it has access to. “A” in Figure 11 represents the client application.

- **Orderer node:** These nodes are in charge of adding new transactions and data to the blockchain in form of blocks. It is needed one per blockchain, but it is possible to add more. These nodes are denoted in Figure 11 by “O”.
- **Admins:** Every organization has an admin who can change some channel configurations (“CC”) and in some cases the network configuration (“NC”). “R” in Figure 11 represents the Admins.
- **Address:** To interact with smart contracts, the Client Applications use their address to identify themselves. The address is the last 160 bits of the result of the sha-3 256 of the IoT device public key.

Figure 11: Diagram of Hyperledger Fabric from⁸

For more information, we refer the reader to the HLF documentation⁹.

3.2.2.2 Component Identity Form

Please, refer to “D3.2: The COLLABS Level-2 Security Package for Resilience in Smart Factories: 1st complete version” [16] for the component identity form.

3.2.2.3 Integration

This component has two integrations plans. One is related with “Fine-Grained authorization based on ABE and Blockchain”, and the other with “Blockchain-based supply chain management system”.

For more information, please refer to “D3.2: The COLLABS Level-2 Security Package for Resilience in Smart Factories: 1st complete version” [16]

3.2.3 IoT CA

3.2.3.1 Functional Description

The IoT CA is a smart contract that stores the addresses of the trusted IoT nodes. Only the owner of the smart contract can modify it. At first, the owner is the smart contract’s creator, but the ownership can

⁸ <https://hyperledger-fabric.readthedocs.io/en/release-2.2/network/network.html>

⁹ <https://hyperledger-fabric.readthedocs.io/>

be transferred. The advantages of use IoT CA deployed in the blockchain is that we receive information of the cycle life of every IoT devices verified by the blockchain. The functionality is simple: the requester asks to the IoT CA for and IoT device ID, and it answer in a binary way if it is valid or not. Due it is a smart contract, the availability is ensured. For the Component Identity Form refer to [36].

3.2.3.2 Integration

This component is deployed in the blockchain as a smart contract written in Solidity, therefore it can be easily deployed in any blockchain that supports or uses the EVM.

3.2.4 Hash Message Broker

3.2.4.1 Functional Description

The hash message broker is a smart contract that stores the metadata (including digest) of all the messages stored in the message broker and links it to the sender of this metadata. Before accepting a metadata packet, the sender address has to be validated by asking the IoT CA.

3.2.4.2 Component Identity Form

Please, refer to “D3.2: The COLLABS Level-2 Security Package for Resilience in Smart Factories: 1st complete version” [16] for the component identity form.

3.2.4.3 Integration

This component is deployed in the blockchain as a smart contract written in Solidity, therefore it can be easily deployed in any blockchain that support or use EVM.

On the other hand, to help the test of the full system, a modified Hash Message Broker was created, `Hash_Message_broker_debugger`, in which a hash already deployed, which enables the reading process of a pre-set message without the necessity of IoT CA for the debug process.

3.2.5 Policies Server

3.2.5.1 Functional Description

The IoT nodes have to encrypt their message before sending them to the message broker using the ABE Policies. The IoT nodes receive these policies from the Policies Server.

3.2.5.2 Component Identity Form

We provide the component identity form for the Policies Server in Table 6.

Table 6: Component Description for the Policies Server

Component Name	Policies server
Functionality	
Keeps an update list of the IoT devices groups policies.	
Pre-condition	
The user owner has to keep the list updated.	
Post-condition	
The IoT devise will ask for its policy before encrypting a message.	
Interoperability and Interaction Component List	
IComponent Name	Input and Output
Sensor owner	Sensor owner → Policies server: Update the policies and encryption keys.
IoT device	Policies server → IoT device: Send the encryption keys

3.2.5.3 Integration

This component is deployed in the blockchain as a smart contract written in Solidity, therefore it can be easily deployed in any blockchain that supports or uses the EVM.

3.2.6 Requirements (CSR fulfilment)

We provide the pertinent security requirements in Table 7. Blockchain and Inter-Ledgers covers Cross-Cutting CSR-13, 15, 16 and 23.

Table 7: Common Security Requirements (CSR) - Blockchains and Interledgers

CSRs	Coverage	Technology Mapping
CSR-01: Identification and Authentication	Fully	It grants access to authorized member only. Moreover, it implements mechanisms (e.g. channels and private data) to provide fine-grained access control
CSR-02: State-of-the-art cryptography	Fully	The system is based on HLF which uses TLS for intra component communication. Moreover, each organization uses its own CA to grant access to its member
CSR-04: Authorization (least privilege)	Fully	The system is structured with channels and private data to strictly enforce least knowledge principle
CSR-05: Identity and access control management	Partial	The system is currently integrated with CAs, however further integration of IAM components and account management can be envisioned

CSR-06: Fine-grained access control support	Partial	The system is structured with channels and private data to strictly enforce fine-grained access control. A possible integration of ABE can be envisioned
CSR-07: Logging	Fully	The system is blockchain-based and keeps record of each interaction with the component
CSR-09: Accountability and non-repudiation	Fully	The system is blockchain-based and keeps record of each interaction with the component with strong non-repudiation guarantees
CSR-10: System integrity protection	Fully	All the interactions with the system are validated through the smart contract (which is approved by the participants). In order to change it we need a consensus on the new version
CSR-11: Data integrity protection	Fully	The ledger is immutable and the integrity in time is guarantee
CSR-13: Protection against denial-of-service	Partial	The system shall be protected against system/service degradation (e.g., individual components); e.g., protection against denial-of-service. The service is distributed and provides guarantees against service degradation when participants are unavailable or maliciously acting (majority consensus)
CSR-14: Data availability	Partial	Redundant copies of the ledger (data) are stored in a distributed environment availability (on all the peers) ensuring data
CSR-15: Online patching and update capabilities	Fully	The blockchain peers accept updates, and it will not affect to the rest of the system if there are still variables peers. Moreover, the chaincodes can be updated with the agreement of most organizations
CSR-16: Fail-safe configuration	Partial	If an individual node has a problem, it can be restarted, and through an update communicating with the rest of the available nodes will get the current status of the blockchain.
CSR-23: Cybersecurity development best practices	Fully	Hyperledger Fabric is a validated secure infrastructure from Linux foundation. It uses the state of the art cryptography for identifications and authorizations.

In Table 8 we provide the software requirements for the Hyperledger Fabric.

Table 8: Hyperledger Fabric Modules Software Requirements

Hyperledger Fabric module software requirements:Name	Vendor	Version	Reference
Go	Google	1.13.x	https://go.dev/
Git	Software Freedom Conservancy	2.29.2	https://git-scm.com/
cURL	cURL	7.73.0	https://curl.se/
Wget	GNU project	1.20	https://www.gnu.org/software/wget

Docker	Docker	17.06.2	https://www.docker.com/get-docker
Python	Python Software Foundation	2.7	https://www.python.org/
NodeJS	OpenJS Foundation	10.15.3	https://nodejs.org/

3.2.7 Future Work

The component “Fine-Grained authorization based on ABE and Blockchain” is using the version Hyperledger Fabric 1.4, however other components in the project COLLABS uses Hyperledger Fabric 2.2. The future work in “Blockchains and Inter-Ledgers” is adapt all the blockchain to the same version to increase the compatibility.

3.3 Public Key Infrastructures

3.3.1 Overview

For the normal operation of the labs of every scenario, the owner will deploy their own CA, which will help in the integration process and since all the CAs work with the same certificate standard, no problems will be found.

However, the IoT devices has problem to works in secure environments due to the untrusted key management. For that propose, in the 1st complete version, the device Optiga TPM2.0 was deployed. The cryptographic hardware was used in the IoT devices ensuring the correct integration of the IoT devices in the labs’ PKI. In the final release a system was created to register and manage the IoT nodes’ crypto material remotely allowing to safety enrol in the PKIs of the laboratories.

On the other hand, a novel system has been proposed to manage public key in the blockchain. It allows the blockchain to also act as a CA, providing to the system integrity protection, high Availability and dynamism.

3.3.2 Optiga TPM

3.3.2.1 Functional Description

The Optiga TPM is a hardware security module that follows the standard Trusted Platform Module 2.0 (TPM 2.0) developed by TCG. This module supports several cryptographic algorithms, has a TRNG, and secure private key management, disk encryption, and allows measured boot.

We use the device TPM “IRIDIUM9670 TPM2.0 LINUX”. This component is used with SPI and is designed to directly plug it in a Raspberry Pi. Thanks to this component, we can trust the IoT devices credentials and therefore, their infrastructures interactions.

3.3.2.2 Integration

A TPM2.0 device can be deployed in any PKI that makes use of X.509 certificates. A guide to deploy the TPM in IoT devices and create certification signing requests has been provided to favour the integration of the IoT devices in secure environments and any PKI.

The Optiga TPM2.0 have been successfully integrated into a client of the blockchain of the Blockchain-based supply chain management system and in a client of Fine-Grained authorization based on ABE and Blockchain. The component has been deployed on a Raspberry PI 4B connected to the shop floor of the ALES laboratory. For technical details, please refer to “The COLLABS Level-1 Security Package for Securely Connected Objects: Final Version” [37]

3.3.3 Key provisioning for Remote attestation

3.3.3.1 Functional Description

One of the most important elements of Remote attestation through TPM is the remote enrolment. The Remote attestation through TPM’s goal, as remote attestation system, is to provide trust in the device to attest. The enrolment of a device in a remote attestation infrastructure is a very delicate process, which is why, in the state of the art, it is omitted on the assumption that it has been done offline and while the device was trusted.

This has consequences, making enrolment in a new infrastructure complex and requiring physical access to the device if maintenance or restarting the process is required.

Remote attestation through TPM has implemented a novel enrolment system, where despite the device being considered untrusted throughout the process, secret keys can be generated on the device, validated and certified, knowing that it complies with the security requirements needed for Remote attestation through TPM.

The owner of the device can deploy it wherever it considers. Because the remote enrolment, the process is completely scalable.

Once the device is deployed, the Verifier has to assert the device's hardware Root of Trust, and manage the creation and validation of some special keys in the Attestor. It is a completely remote process and can be realized even in an untrusted Attestor. Therefore, the role of Verifier can be dynamically changed, and even multiple Verifiers can work at the same time sharing the trust and responsibility.

At the end of the process, the device obtains a key and a certificate that identifies it and its integrity to the rest of the infrastructure, for example in a blockchain infrastructure.

3.3.3.2 Component Identity Form

Table 9: Component Identity Form for Remote attestation key provisioning

Component Name	Key provisioning for Remote attestation
Functionality	
<p>This method is part of Remote attestation through TPM, it is highly recommended reading the section “Remote attestation through TPM, 3.2.3 Remote Attestation and Secure C&C execution on IIoT Devices, The COLLABS Level-1 Security Package for Securely Connected Objects: 1st complete version” before reading this chapter.</p>	
<p>This process explains the crypto-data transferring for correct and reliable functionality of the system Remote attestation through TPM. The goals behind this key provisioning are to verify that the TPM</p>	

devices were made by a reliable TPM manufacturer to avoid forgery or phishing, to allow on-the-fly personalized access policies, and to restrict the IoT device access to the PKI.

Endorsement key (Ek):

When a TPM is made, the private endorsement key is randomly generated inside of it, the TPM manufacturer signs it (Ek certificate) to prove it is a genuine TPM and store it in the TPM. Because of privacy concerns, this key cannot be used for signatures.

Process:

Once the IoT device has been deployed. It proves it is a trusted IoT device manufactured showing the manufactory certificates, the TPM credentials and the EK public key (EKPubK). Moreover, the TPM creates an “Attestation key” (AK) and proves the correct creation to the verifier. The AK is a special TPM key used to validate all the operations and states of the TPM. When the Verifier, assert this information, it can trust in the hardware IoT device and in the TPM operations.

Using the attestation key, the Verifier can assert the correct creation of the Sealed key in the TPM. It is a special key that can be used just if the Verifier authorize it, and can be used as long as the IoT device status does not change. The authorizations are signed by the Verifier and flexible, therefore, only the Verifier can authorize the use and it accepts software updates.

Pre-condition	
Correct IoT device hardware	
Post-condition	
Continuous conditions-fulfilled: With this key provisioning, compliance with the conditions imposed by the challenger is guaranteed in each interaction of the IoT device with the PKI	
Interaction Component List	
IComponent Name	Input and Output
Certification Authority	The Attestor device will have to send the CSR to a CA and get the certificate back in the same controlled session.

3.3.3.3 Integration

This technology is deployed with Remote attestation through TPM, please refer to “The COLLABS Level-1 Security Package for Securely Connected Objects: Final Version” for more information [37].

3.3.4 Revocation binary tree

3.3.4.1 Functional Description

The component “Fine-Grained authorization based on ABE and Blockchain” is very novel component because it is able to provide a revocation solution for Attribute Based Encryption. This revocation is done through Indirect Revocation.

Indirect Revocation enforces revocation updating all the keys of the non-revoked users and the encryption protocols, hence revoked users loose access to the encrypted data. The problem with this method is that it requires a constant update of non-revoked users' credentials and when the number of users is high enough, it can lead to a key provisioning system overload.

To solve this problem, we developed a Revocation binary tree. We take advantage that our system is using a specific ABE algorithm [38] that allows us the use of an unlimited number of attributes. Therefore, providing specific attributes to the users, and changing the policies, we can revoke a small group of the users, easing the burden on the key provisioning system.

3.3.4.2 Component Identity Form

Table 10: Component Identity Form for Revocation binary tree

Component Name	Revocation binary tree
Functionality	

To use the Revocation binary tree, a variable-level binary tree is first generated. In the example of image 6, a binary tree of level 3 is used. The final branches of the binary tree are the number of groups in which the users are divided. Each branch can have an indefinite number of users. The more levels, the more leaves and therefore, more groups. Each user is granted additional attributes called the revocation attributes which unequivocally define the group to which they belong, and the version of the revocation. When a single user in a group is to be revoked, such as User2 in our example, the revocation policy is added to all messages, so that all groups except the revoked group can satisfy this policy. In our example, this new revocation policy is [7 or 4 or 2 or V2]. The non-revoked users of the revoked group must be granted new keys with new revocation attributes so that none of those that the revoked user had is repeated. In our example, User10's new revocation attributes are [8V1,3V1,1V1, V2]. Due to the particular ABE algorithm used, the total number of attributes in the system does not affect the public encryption keys.

Figure 12: Example of the functionality of Revocation binary tree.

Pre-condition

This system of key revocation requires a continuous update of the policies of the writers. In Fine-Grained authorization based on ABE and Blockchain, policies are published on the blockchain. Due to the security characteristics of the blockchain (integrity, authenticity, and availability), we consider this condition is satisfied.

Post-condition

Fine-Grained authorization based on ABE and Blockchain is scalable with respect to the number of users

Interaction Component List

IComponent Name	Input and Output
-----------------	------------------

Sensor owner	Sensor Owner provide an updated information about the list of users.
Policy Server	Revocation binary tree provide as output the current revocation policy.

3.3.4.3 Integration

This technology is designed to adapt “Fine-Grained authorization based on ABE and Blockchain” to a large number of users (2000 of higher) but it is not a fundamental necessity in any of the proposed scenarios therefore the integration is not planned for the second release.

3.3.5 Requirements (CSR fulfilment)

Public Key Infrastructures covers Cross-Cutting CSR-13 and 23 (see Table 11).

Table 11: Common Security Requirements (CSR) - Public Key Infrastructures

CSRs	Coverage	Technology Mapping
CSR-01: Identification and Authentication	Fully	The system provides the needed authentication for granting or refusing access to the services.
CSR-02: State-of-the-art cryptography	Fully	All the cryptographic solutions are based in state-of-the-art cryptography.
CSR-07: Logging	Partially	The system provide authentication for entities easing the logging and tracking.
CSR-09: Accountability and non-repudiation	Partially	The system provide authentication for entities easing the logging traceability and auditability.
CSR-11: Data integrity protection	Partially	A good authentication of the entities is essential for digital signatures and hence for data integrity
CSR-13: Protection against denial-of-service	Partially	Through the use of certificates and decentralization, a DoS attack will not affect to the correct functionality of the system in short term.
CSR-18: Confidentiality wrt. cloud	Partially	The PKI provide an essential labor for key providing and therefore to confidentiality.
CSR-20: Plug-and-work security configuration	Partially	All the processes are developed to allow an easy utilization and configuration.

CSR-23: Cybersecurity development best practices	Partially	Using the well-known TPM standard, some of the individual components are following the best practices in Hardware Security Modules.
---	-----------	---

3.3.6 Future Work

As part of the integration section, we plan to integrate the Key provisioning for Remote attestation with an enrolment in blockchain. It would enable the integration of Remote attestation through the TPM with Fine-Grained authorization based on ABE and Blockchain.

3.4 Confidential Data Discovery

3.4.1 Overview

In the network traffic domain, there are two main approaches for monitoring and security analysis: signature-based and behaviour-based. Signature-based approach is based on monitoring of inbound network traffic in order to find sequences or patterns that match a particular attack signature. The main characteristics of this approach are:

- Fast execution and easy implementation
- Requires signature for each suspicious traffic pattern or network attack (and expert to identify them)
- Requires accurate model definitions. A loose interpretation will generate false negatives while too strict interpretation will increase the percentage of false positives identifications.

On the other hand, a behaviour-based approach creates a shape of normal network activity and compares the new traffic with a learned model in order to detect unusual patterns in network activity. This type of network monitoring system uses AI and machine learning for analysing data on a network.

The COLLABS CDD component combines both strategies with an adaptive feature selection approach. Component could be used for detection of suspicious network traffic but also for discovering the confidential data in the packet payload (if this is achievable - unencrypted traffic). Such a setup could be used within the COLLABS framework for confidential data discovery on various sources including data from sensors, IoT fingerprints, device activity patterns, network traffic data (packet lengths, IP/MAC addresses, timestamps, directions, packet inter-arrival times) and also emails, files, databases, etc.

3.4.2 Components of CDD

The CDD component implements a network traffic analysis framework which is able to identify sensitive or confidential information and generate alarms when unusual activities or new access patterns occur. Input for this component is raw network packet data and outputs are events that represent intrusion detection, detection of malicious activity or confidential data leaks. The functionality relies on the following 3 components:

- Network traffic processing component
- Feature selection and data transformation module (ML based)
- Machine-learning classification module

80tcp515670 443tcp4044370 15432sslv34431456,R
 443tcp4044370 15432sslv34431456 44854tcp44370,R
 15432sslv34431456 44854tcp44370 443tcp714670,R
 44854tcp44370 443tcp714670 443tcp4885170,R
 443tcp714670 443tcp4885170 60347tcp44370,R
 ...
 546dhcpv6547146 546dhcpv6547146 546dhcpv6547146,I
 546dhcpv6547146 546dhcpv6547146 62027dns5376,I
 546dhcpv6547146 62027dns5376 62027dns5376,I
 62027dns5376 62027dns5376 62027icmp53104,I
 62027dns5376 62027icmp53104 62027dns5376,I
 62027icmp53104 62027dns5376 546dhcpv6547146,I

Figure 14: NLP based ML model create a vectorized representation for each n-gram

The benefits of such approach are two-fold:

- On the feature level, it enables usage of protocol/domain specific features. This will improve our ML models for behavior-based anomaly detection by overcoming the fuzzy representations with protocol independent features.
- On the application level, it enables utilization of light-weighted ML models, designed for specific network’s topics. Consequently, this will enable distributed processing

3.4.2.2 Component Identity Form

Table 12: Component Identity Form for Confidential Data Discovery

Component Name	Confidential Data Discovery
Functionality	
Network traffic analysis framework which is able to identify sensitive or confidential information and generate alarms when unusual activities or new access patterns occur.	
Pre-condition	
Native OS or VM able to execute Python and dependent libraries. For training, the component requires labelled input data in the form of pcap files. For inference, direct network read should be provided.	
Post-condition	
There are no specific postconditions.	
Interaction Component List	
IComponent Name	Input and Output
Interactive Visualization	OUTPUT

3.4.3 Integration

CDD component provides an appropriate and effective way to monitor and analyse network packet data in a smart factory environment. This component implements a predictive model which should communicate with the dedicated network infrastructure in order to access to network packets from factory environment (Network packet provider - NPP). Additionally, it might be connected to Interactive Visualization component in order to send event when suspicious activity or confidential data leakage is detected. RESTful services can be used for communication, but many other protocols can be implemented.

3.4.4 Performance Evaluation

CDD component performance is evaluated on open access data containing malicious activity or policy violations. IoT Network Intrusion Dataset (<https://iee-dataport.org/open-access/iot-network-intrusion-dataset>). This dataset contains various types of network attacks in Internet of Things (IoT) environment, represented by 42 raw network packet files (pcap) at different time points. There are four attack categories that can be divided into eight subcategories. Packets that belong to these categories represent training dataset for malicious traffic.

After ML model training, testing is done by putting the test set of those files through the CDD component. For particular categories (for example ARP attacks detection), components achieved 97% accuracy in tests with two classes - regular and irregular network traffic.

4 Ethics of Artificial Intelligence

Deliverable 1.4 examines the applicability of the European Commission's ethical guidelines for proper usage of artificial intelligence to COLLABS project. As part of the work done within the deliverable, an evaluation of the guidelines was performed using a questionnaire defined for these purposes. The questionnaire is partitioned into two parts - the perspective of the AI tools providers, and the perspective of the AI tools users. Following ethical aspects have been covered: human agency and oversight, technical robustness and safety, privacy and data governance, transparency, diversity, non-discrimination and fairness, societal and environmental well-being and accountability. In this regard, a description of Artificial Intelligence (AI) usage within COLLABS WP2 components has been given below.

The only component in this work package that uses artificial intelligence is the Confidential Data Discovery component. One of the objectives of this component is the detection of situations where any personal or confidential information has leaked and can be found unencrypted in network packets being exchanged by the other components of the system. Methods used for designing and developing the algorithms within those components have been described in all details in project deliverables. The component logs all its activities and have satisfactory level of protection within the infrastructure it will be deployed on.

5 Summary and Conclusion

This document is the final outcome of COLLABS WP3.

The Work Package activities were organized around 4 tasks:

- T3.1 about Comprehensive Access Control
- T3.2 about Blockchain and Inter-Ledgers
- T3.3 about Public Key Infrastructures
- T3.4 about Confidential Data Discovery

These tasks lead to the design and implementation of innovative technologies dedicated to their related subject, and their translation into the Security Components described in section 3.

These new technologies have been put together to serve the security challenges of Industry 4.0, into the building of the three security features: a blockchain-and-ABE-based fine-grained authorization system, a blockchain-based supply chain management system, and a machine-learning based tool for confidential data discovery. These features constitute the Level-2 Security Package for Resilience in Smart Factories, described in Section 2. In this section is also described the relevance of these features in real-world use case scenarios proposed by Collins Aerospace, Renault and Philips Consumer.

Moreover, this document mentions the Common Security Requirements (CSR) which are covered by the security components. The full list and description of COLLABS CSR can be found in deliverable “D1.2: System Architecture of COLLABS” [39]. Some of them are cross-cutting, especially the CSR-13, 15, 16 and 23, which must be covered at a more global level. According to information provided this document, we can summarize that CSR-13, about protection against denial-of-service, is covered by the decentralized aspect of IPFS and the blockchain-based technologies; CSR-15, about online patching and update capabilities, is ensured by the blockchain-based configuration along with a deployment as Docker container; CSR-16, about fail-safe configuration, is covered by the recovery capacities of a blockchain node in a blockchain-based technology. CSR-23, about best practices usage, is ensured by the support of the well-known TPM standard.

To conclude, this document illustrates the scientific breakthrough done in the different fields of study of the WP3. Among them, the use of attribute-based encryption, new cryptographic system, to enable fine-grained, lightweight, end-to-end and multi-tenant confidentiality and access control to industrial systems data; the use of blockchain, along with attribute-based encryption, to add integrity, authentication, accountability and revocation aspects to this industrial data protection system. Another innovation is the use of blockchain to follow details of the manufacturing process of safety critical products, through authenticated and unforgeable traces. Moreover, TPMs have been integrated in edge devices for interacting with distributed ledger technologies, and used along with a distributed PKI, reinforcing the system integrity and the trust in the IoT devices representation in the ledger. Finally, another innovation is the usage of deep learning methods in industrial data communication networks to detect confidential data leakage, with a transformation of raw packet data, through NLP approach, into a vectorized representation of each packet.

6 Bibliography

- [1] N. Mohamed and J. Al-Jaroodi, "Applying Blockchain in Industry 4.0 Applications," in *2019 IEEE 9th Annual Computing and Communication Workshop and Conference (CCWC)*, 2019.
- [2] Y. Zuo, "Making smart manufacturing smarter - a survey on blockchain technology in Industry 4.0," 2020.
- [3] I. U. H. Anum Mushtaq, "Implications of Blockchain in Industry 4.0," 2019.
- [4] V. Goyal, O. Pandey, A. Sahai and B. Waters, "Attribute-based encryption for fine-grained access control of encrypted data," in *CCS*, 2006.
- [5] O. Source, "IPFS," [Online]. Available: <https://ipfs.io/>.
- [6] O. Pinno, A. Gregio and L. De Bona, "ControlChain: Blockchain as a Central Enabler for Access Control Authorizations in the IoT," in *IEEE Global Communications Conference GLOBECOM*, Singapore, 2017.
- [7] OpenID, "OpenID Connect," [Online]. Available: <https://openid.net/connect/>.
- [8] N. Attrapadung and H. Imai, "Attribute-based encryption supporting direct/indirect revocation modes," *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol. 5921, p. 78-300, 2009.
- [9] A. Lewko, A. Sanaïs and B. Waters, "Revocation systems with verysmall private keys," *IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy*, 2010.
- [10] Y. Li, J. Zhu, X. Wang, Y. Chai and S. Shao, "Optimized Ciphertext-Policy Attribute-Based Encryption with Efficient Revocation," *International Journal of Security and Its Applications*,, 2013.
- [11] Y. Rahulamathavan, R. C. Phan, M. Rajarajan, S. Misra and A. Kondo, "Privacy-preserving blockchain based IoT ecosystem using attribute-based encryption," *IEEE International Conference on Advanced Networks and Telecommunications Systems*, 2018.
- [12] G. Wood, "Ethereum: A Secure Decentralised Generalised Transaction Ledger - Petersburg Version," *Ethereum Project Yellow Paper*, 2020.
- [13] S. Wang, Y. Zhang and Y. Zhang, "A blockchain-based framework for data sharing with fine-grained access control in decentralized storage systems," *IEEE Access*, 2018.
- [14] R. Guo, H. Shi, D. Zheng, C. Jing, C. Zhuang and Z. Wang, "Flexible and Efficient Blockchain-Based ABE Scheme with Multi-Authority for Medical on Demand in Telemedicine System," *IEEE Access*, 2019.
- [15] RedHat, "Keycloak," [Online]. Available: <https://www.keycloak.org/>.

- [16] COLLABS, Deliverable "D3.2: The COLLABS Level-2 Security Package for Resilience in Smart Factories: 1st complete version", 2021.
- [17] COLLABS, "Deliverable "D6.2: COLLABS Demonstration - Final execution",", 2022.
- [18] H.-C. Pfohl, B. Yahsi and T. Kurnaz, "The impact of industry 4.0 on the supply chain," *Innovations and Strategies for Logistics and Supply Chains: Technologies, Business Models and Risk Management. Proceedings of the Hamburg International Conference of Logistics (HICL)*, 2015.
- [19] M. K. J. S. a. L. S. S. Saberi, "Blockchain technology and its relationships to sustainable supply chain management," *International Journal of Production Research*, 2018.
- [20] C. S. M. K. a. S. W. S. Kurpjuweit, "Blockchain in additive manufacturing and its impact on supply chains," *Journal of Business Logistics*, 2019.
- [21] K. P. a. A.-U.-H. Yasar, "Internet of things and blockchain technology in apparel manufacturing supply chain data management".*Procedia Computer Science*.
- [22] Y. M. a. P. Panfilov, "Blockchain And Supply Chain Management: Aircrafts' Parts' Business Case," 2017.
- [23] Y. Wang, Y. Xiang, W. Zhou and S. Yu, "Generating regular expression signatures for network traffic classification in trusted network management," *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 992-1000, 2012.
- [24] G. P. M. A. S. M. E. P. & I. S. Vasiliadis, "Regular expression matching on graphics hardware for intrusion detection," in *In International Workshop on Recent Advances in Intrusion Detection*, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2009.
- [25] S. N. G. a. V. M. T. Girish M. Wandhare, "Network intrusion detection technique for regular expression detection using dpi in AD-HOC wireless network," *International Journal of Current Research*, vol. 7, no. 11, pp. 22371-22382, 2015.
- [26] A. B. R. K. N. H. B. N. N. & J. R. Tuor, "Recurrent neural network language models for open vocabulary event-level cyber anomaly detection," *arXiv*, p. arXiv:1712.00557, 2017.
- [27] B. J. A. L. M. T. A. J. & S. J. A. Radford, "Network traffic anomaly detection using recurrent neural networks," *arXiv*, p. arXiv:1803.10769, 2018.
- [28] R. M. F. G.-D. A. M. J. H. F. N. S. & N. M. Gonzalez, "Net2Vec: Deep Learning for the Network," in *Proceedings of the Workshop on Big Data Analytics and Machine Learning for Data Communication Networks*, 2017.
- [29] COLLABS, Deliverable "D3.1: The COLLABS Level-2 Security Package for Resilience in Smart Factories: MVP", 2020.
- [30] A. Singla and E. Bertino, "Blockchain-based PKI solutions for IoT," in *IEEE 4th International Conference on Collaboration and Internet Computing (CIC)*, Philadelphia, PA, 2018.

- [31] A. Yakubov, W. Shbair, A. Wallbom, D. Sanda and R. State, “A blockchain based PKI management framework,” in *IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium*, Taipei, 2018.
- [32] Y. Yu, Y. Li, J. Tian and Liu, “Blockchain-based solutions to security and privacy issues in the Internet of Things,” *IEEE Wireless Communications*, pp. 12-18, 2018.
- [33] “Eth Gas Station Blog,” [Online].
- [34] Open-Source, “ethereum.org,” <https://ethereum.org/>, March 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://ethereum.org/en/developers/docs/evm/>.
- [35] “Hyperledger,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.hyperledger.org/>.
- [36] COLLABS, Deliverable “D4.1: The COLLABS Level-1 Security Package for Securely Connected Objects: MVP”, submitted, 2020.
- [37] COLLABS, D4.3: The COLLABS Level-1 Security Package for Securely Connected Objects: Final Version, 2022.
- [38] B. Waters, “Ciphertext-Policy Attribute-Based Encryption: An Expressive, Efficient, and Provably Secure Realization,” 2008.
- [39] COLLABS, “D1.2 System Architecture definition,” 2020.
- [40] P. Vingelmann and F. H. Fitzek, “CUDA, release: 10.2.89,” 2020.
- [41] B. Tang, H. Kang, J. Fan, Q. Li and R. Sandhu, “IoT Passport: A Blockchain-Based Trust Framework for Collaborative Internet-of-Things,” in *24th ACM Symposium on Access Control Models and Technologies*, 2019.
- [42] V. Hu, D. Ferraiolo, R. Kuhn, A. Friedman, A. Lang, M. Cogdell, A. Schnitzer, K. Sandlin, R. Miller and K. Scarfone, “Guide to Attribute Based Access Controls (ABAC) Definitions and Considerations (Draft),” NIST Special Publication 800-162, 2013.
- [43] M. Ghobakhloo, “Industry 4.0, digitization, and opportunities for sustainability,” 2020.
- [44] e. a. Elli Androulaki, “Hyperledger Fabric: A Distributed Operating System for Permissioned Blockchains”.
- [45] H. Lasi, P. Fettke, H. G. Kemper, T. Feld and M. Hoffmann, “Industry 4.0. Business & information systems engineering,” 2014.
- [46] L. Ardito, A. Petruzzelli, U. Panniello and A. Garavelli, “Towards Industry 4.0: mapping digital technologies for supply chain management-marketing integration”.
- [47] W. S. Alaloul, M. S. Liew, N. A. W. A. Zawawi and B. S. Mohammed, “Industry Revolution IR 4.0: Future Opportunities and Challenges in Construction Industry,” in *MATEC web of conferences*, 2018.

[48] V. Goyal, O. Pandey, A. Sahai and B. Waters, “Attribute-based encryption for fine-grained access control of encrypted data,” *CCS*, 2006.

[49] COLLABS, “COLLABS, Deliverable “D1.1: Positioning of the COLLABS”,” 2020.